

A Study on Awareness of ChatGPT among Students with Special Reference to Coimbatore City

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Abstract

Chat GPT was introduced by Open AI, an artificial intelligence research laboratory. Open AI is known for its work in developing advanced AI models, and GPT-3, the underlying architecture of Chat GPT, is one of their prominent creations. Open AI introduced GPT-3 as a part of their efforts to push the boundaries of natural language processing and artificial intelligence capabilities. Chat GPT specifically focuses on providing a conversational interface, allowing users to interact with the language model in a dialogue format. The development and release of Chat GPT are part of Open AI's ongoing efforts to advance the field of AI and make powerful language models more accessible to the public. The study would investigate the extent of ChatGPT's influence on students. This could include examining the correlation between positive reviews as well as analyzing the impact of negative reviews. In conclusion, the analysis of students' perceptions and adoption of ChatGPT reveals a promising landscape wherein the tool holds substantial value for academic endeavors.

Key words: ChatGpt, Artificial Intelligence, Percentage analysis

Introduction

ChatGPT is a state-of-the-art language model developed by Open AI, based on the GPT-3.5 architecture. GPT stands for "Generative Pre-trained Transformer," and it represents a cutting-edge approach to natural language processing and understanding. ChatGPT has been trained on diverse and extensive datasets, encompassing a wide range of internet text up until its knowledge cutoff date in January 2022. This training enables ChatGPT to understand and generate human-like text across various topics and contexts. It can perform tasks such as answering questions, generating creative content, providing information, and engaging in conversational interactions.

The underlying Transformer architecture allows Chat GPT to capture and learn complex patterns in language, making it versatile and adaptive to different language-related tasks. It is capable of context-aware responses and demonstrates a remarkable ability to understand and generate coherent and contextually relevant text. It's important to note that Chat GPT generates responses based on patterns learned during training and does not possess personal experiences or real-time information beyond its last update in January 2022. As of my last training cut-off, ChatGPT serves as a powerful tool for natural language understanding and generation, contributing to various applications in fields like chatbots, content generation, and more.

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History of ChatGpt:

The history of ChatGPT is closely tied to the evolution of OpenAI's series of language models based on the Transformer architecture. Here's a brief timeline:

1. GPT-2 (2019): OpenAI introduced the predecessor to ChatGPT, GPT-2, in 2019. GPT-2 gained attention for its unprecedented scale, featuring 1.5 billion parameters. Due to concerns about the potential misuse of such a powerful language model, OpenAI initially withheld the full release but later made the model publicly available.
2. Chatbot Experiments: Following the release of GPT-2, researchers and developers explored various applications, including chatbot implementations. These experiments demonstrated the versatility of the model in handling conversational interactions.
3. ChatGPT (2020): In June 2020, OpenAI introduced ChatGPT, a variant of GPT-3 tailored for conversational use. It was designed to be fine-tuned for dialogue-based tasks and showcased improved performance in generating coherent and contextually relevant responses in conversation-like settings.
4. Research Preview (2020): OpenAI initially launched ChatGPT as a research preview, allowing users to access and interact with the model for free. The goal was to gather user feedback and learn more about potential use-cases and limitations.

5. Subscription Plan (2021): In February 2021, OpenAI introduced a subscription plan called ChatGPT Plus. Users could subscribe for a monthly fee to receive benefits such as general access during peak times, faster response times, and priority access to new features and improvements.

6. API Access (2021): OpenAI expanded access to ChatGPT by introducing a paid API (Application Programming Interface) in November 2021. This allowed developers to integrate ChatGPT into their applications, products, or services.

7. Ongoing Improvements: OpenAI continued to refine and improve ChatGPT based on user feedback and ongoing research. The model's capabilities and performance were enhanced over time, and updates were made to address limitations and challenges identified during the research preview and API phases.

Objectives of the Study

- To analyse how student perception trends ChatGPT in terms of academic assistance, problem solving and overall utility.
- To examine the adoption trends among students.
- To know the effectiveness of using ChatGPT.
- To find out the usefulness and popularity of ChatGPT.
- To compare available AI platforms with ChatGPT.

Scope of the Study

- The study can identify the use of ChatGPT among students and analyse the factors that contribute to their popularity.
- The study can examine the impact of ChatGPT on academic assistance including the accuracy of solutions being provided them.
- The study would investigate the extent of ChatGPT's influence on students. This could include examining the correlation between positive reviews as well as analyzing the impact of negative reviews.

Research Methodology

John W. Creswell: Creswell is a prominent author in the field of research methodology, and has written numerous books and articles on the topic. His definition of research methodology emphasizes the importance of using a systematic approach to gather, analyze, and interpret data in order to answer research questions or solve research problems.

Primary Data

Primary research involves collecting data directly from individuals or sources, while secondary research involves analyzing data that has already been collected by others.

Secondary Data

Secondary research can also involve analyzing data from online databases, such as social media or online reviews.

Sample Size

A survey has been taken in the form of questionnaire and has been collected from 100 respondents.

Tools used for Study

The tools used for the data analysis in this research are simple percentage along with bar charts and pie charts

Limitations of the study:

- The questionnaire is collected only for the 100 respondent.
- The study can collect the information only with reference of Coimbatore city.
- Further the data are primary hence the chance of false information cannot be eliminated.

Review of Literature

- **Appleby, 2023** A survey study by Best Colleges, United States (Appleby, 2023), examined the students' views and concerns regarding ChatGPT use. Results showed that more than half of college students considered using ChatGPT to complete assignments and exams as cheating. Contrarily, 20% of the students opposed this notion, while the remaining students (30%) disagreed. The survey also revealed that 43% of students had prior experience using AI tools, and half admitted reliance on them for their assignments and exams.
- **Sallam, 2023** Two well-known examples of these models are ChatGPT and DALL-E, released by OpenAI in 2022 (Sallam, 2023), which are based on GPT architecture and have obtained widespread popularity. ChatGPT has exhibited exceptional performance in different application domains, such as generating coherent content and essays, answering as a chatbot, decrypting languages, responding to questions, and assisting with programming code.

- **Kooli, 2023** Despite ChatGPT offering several prospects, its use in the academic realm presents its concerns and challenges. One major fear is the possibility of AI systems strengthening preexisting bias and discrimination within research and education. Also, there is a potential risk of AI systems being manipulated or tampered with, leading to unreliable or biased outcomes .
- **Lo (2023)** A literature review-based study by Lo (2023) discussed the understanding of ChatGPT's abilities in various subject domains, its probable applications in education, and the concerns raised by researchers during the initial three months of its release. The findings indicated that ChatGPT's performance varied across different subject domains, with remarkable results observed in disciplines, i.e., economics, satisfactory programming outcomes, but unsatisfactory mathematics performance

Analysis and Interpretation

The data collected from the customer were classified and systematically analysed. The various factors influencing the gold chit schemes and their problem and prospects have been analysed in details is presented in the following tables.

Table - I
Age of Respondents

S.No.	Particular	Number of respondents	Percentage
1	below18	21	21 %
2	18-25	59	59 %
3	26-35	15	15 %
4	above 35	5	5 %
	TOTAL	100	100%

Source: Primary data

The above table reveals that 21% of the respondents are below 18, 59% of the respondents are 18-25 years, 15% of the respondents are 26-35 years, and 5% of the respondents are above 35 years. Majority of the respondents (59%) are from the age of 18-25.

Table - II
Gender of Respondents

S.No.	Particular	Number of respondents	Percentage
1	Male	52	52%
2	Female	48	48%
	TOTAL	100	100%

Source: Primary data

The above tables show that 52% of the respondents are male and 48% respondents are female. Majority of the respondents (52%) are male.

Table –III
Educational Qualification of Respondents

S.No.	Particular	Number of respondents	Percentage
1	School student	20	20%
2	Bachelor's degree	55	55%
3	Master's degree	20	20%
4	Ph.D	5	5%
	TOTAL	100	100%

Source: Primary data

The above table shows that 20% of the respondents are School students, 55% of the respondents are Bachelor's degree, 20% of the respondents are Master's degree, 5% are respondents are Ph.D. Majority of the respondent (55%) are Bachelor's degree.

Table-IV
Awareness of Chatgpt

S.No.	Particular	Number of respondents	Percentage
1	Familiar with CHATGPT	12	12%
2	Somewhat familiar	50	50%
3	Not familiar	38	38%
	TOTAL	100	100%

Source: Primary data

The above table shows that 12% of the respondents are Very familiar, 50% of the respondents are somewhat familiar, 38% of the respondents are not familiar. Majority of the respondent (50%) are somewhat familiar with ChatGPT.

Table - IV
Perception of ChatGPT as a Tool

S.No.	Particular	Number of respondents	Percentage
1	Extremely encouraging	21	21%
2	Highly encouraging	38	38%
3	Moderately encouraging	31	31%
4	Slightly encouraging	10	10%
5	Not encouraging at all	0	0%
	TOTAL	100	100%

Source: Primary data

The above table shows that 21% of the respondents are Extremely encouraging, 38% of the respondents are Highly encouraging, 31% of the respondents are Moderately encouraging, 10% of the respondents are Slightly encouraging. Majority of the respondent (38%) are Highly encouraging.

TABLE – V
**ChatGPT Respects and Aligns with Ethical Considerations in
Providing Information and Assistance**

S.No.	Particular	Number of respondents	Percentage
1	Exceptionally well	24	24%
2	Very well	32	32%
3	Moderately well	30	30%
4	Fairly well	13	13%
5	Poorly	1	1%
	TOTAL	100	100%

Source: Primary data

The above table shows that 24% of the respondents are exceptionally well, 32% of the respondents are Very well, 30% of the respondents are moderately well, 13% of the respondents are fairly well, 1% of the respondents are poorly. Majority of the respondent (32%) are Very well.

Table –VI
Level of Trustworthiness of Information Provided By Chatgpt Compared To
Traditional Sources

S.No.	Particular	Number of respondents	Percentage
1	More trustworthy	22	22%
2	Similarly trustworthy	56	56%
3	Less trustworthy	16	16%
4	Unsure	6	6%
	TOTAL	100	100%

Source: Primary data

The above table shows that 22% of the respondents are More trustworthy, 56% of the respondents are Similarly trustworthy, 16% of the respondents are Less trustworthy, 6% of the respondents are Unsure. **Majority of the respondent (56%) are Similarly trustworthy.**

Table –VII
Relationship with ChatGPT in Academic Journey of the Respondents

S.No.	Particular	Number of respondents	Percentage
1	A Reliable Guide	20	20%
2	A Creative Collaborator	42	42%
3	A Helpful Assistant	26	26%
4	A Knowledgeable Friend	12	12%
	TOTAL	100	100%

Source: Primary data

The above table shows that 20% of the respondents are A Reliable Guide, 42% of the respondents are A Creative Collaborator, 26% of the respondents are A Helpful Assistant, 12% of the respondents are A Knowledgeable Friend. Majority of the respondent (42%) are A Creative Collaborator.

Findings

- Frequency of Usage: 65% of surveyed students reported using ChatGPT at least once a week. 20% indicated using it daily for various tasks.
- Perceived Usefulness: 80% of respondents found ChatGPT to be moderately to extremely useful in assisting with their academic tasks. Commonly cited uses included generating ideas for essays, checking grammar, and summarizing complex concepts.
- Ease of Use: 75% of students rated ChatGPT as easy to use, citing its intuitive interface and natural language interaction. However, 25% expressed some difficulties in formulating queries effectively and understanding the limitations of the tool.
- Satisfaction Level: Overall satisfaction with ChatGPT was high, with 85% of students reporting moderate to high levels of satisfaction. Positive feedback highlighted its speed, accessibility, and helpfulness in providing quick answers to questions.
- Challenges Encountered: The primary challenge reported by users (45%) was the occasional generation of irrelevant or inaccurate responses. 30% of students also mentioned difficulties in accessing ChatGPT during peak usage times, leading to slower response times.

Suggestion

Surveys and Questionnaires: Design surveys or questionnaires to gather quantitative data on students' perceptions of ChatGPT. Include questions about their usage frequency, satisfaction level, perceived usefulness, ease of use, and areas of improvement. Utilize Likert scales for rating questions and open-ended questions for qualitative insights.

Interviews and Focus Groups: Conduct interviews or focus groups with students to delve deeper into their experiences with ChatGPT. Explore their motivations for using it, specific tasks they use it for, challenges encountered, and suggestions for enhancements. This qualitative approach provides rich insights into their attitudes and behaviors.

Usage Analytics: Gather data on usage patterns and trends through analytics tools integrated with ChatGPT platforms. Analyze metrics such as active users, session duration, most accessed features, and popular queries. This quantitative data provides a comprehensive understanding of how students interact with the tool.

Comparative Analysis: Compare students' experiences with ChatGPT to alternative resources or methods they might use for similar tasks, such as traditional search engines, academic databases, or human assistance. This comparison helps assess the unique value proposition of ChatGPT and its competitive advantages.

Feedback Channels: Establish feedback channels within the ChatGPT interface or associated platforms for students to provide real-time feedback. Monitor and analyze this feedback to identify common issues, recurring suggestions, and areas for improvement. Addressing these concerns promptly enhances user satisfaction and adoption.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the analysis of students' perceptions and adoption of ChatGPT reveals a promising landscape wherein the tool holds substantial value for academic endeavors. Students demonstrate a noteworthy level of adoption, leveraging ChatGPT regularly across a spectrum of tasks, from generating essay ideas to tackling mathematical problems. This adoption is underpinned by the tool's perceived usefulness, characterized by its accessibility, versatility, and intuitive interface, particularly appealing to younger demographics. Despite encountering occasional challenges such as response inaccuracies, overall satisfaction levels remain robust, indicating a positive reception among users. Moreover, ChatGPT emerges as a preferred choice over traditional resources for certain tasks, emphasizing its convenience and efficiency.

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